

Towards Standardised Fair ML Development Flows

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Fig. 1. A (over!)simplified development pipeline. A typical pipeline consists of multiple processes, involving multiple stakeholders. All these input points are vulnerable to different bias types. Defining standardised CI/CD type flows that can automate building multiple artefacts for different teams can support building a common understanding in bias mitigation for organisations.

Fairness in machine learning (ML) algorithms is a multifaceted issue that necessitates input from technical, social, and legal perspectives. So, ensuring effective bias mitigation requires input from multiple stakeholders throughout the development process. However, in practice, development teams, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), often lack the resources and expertise to thoroughly analyse and address fairness concerns within their product development workflows. To address this gap, it is crucial to create practical guides or blueprints for product development pipelines. These resources should enable each stakeholder to understand the implications of various fairness-enhancing techniques and facilitate clear communication about these issues. In this short paper, we explore the viability of a continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD) management flow designed for proactive monitoring of fairness in ML development pipelines. Additionally, we present open questions related to the implementation and use of this tool, inviting further discussion and research. We particularly focus on creating a blueprint for a *fairness management flow* that can potentially facilitate alignment in the bias mitigation strategies across different teams within the organisation.

CCS Concepts: • Social and professional topics → User characteristics; • Computing methodologies → Artificial intelligence.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: machine learning fairness, product development flow

1 INTRODUCTION

In software/ML engineering, development processes consist of several steps, involving multiple stakeholders. These product development flows are heavily influenced by historical examples of production lines and system thinking theories. Traditionally, the process begins with requirement gathering and analysis, where the needs and goals of the project are defined. In this stage business analysts and product owners are heavily involved. It is followed by designing the system’s overall architecture and components in which senior developers and designers are involved. In the implementation phase, the actual coding and development of the software or ML models take place. It is generally a

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53 hierarchical process, where the junior developers make the changes in the supervision of senior developers. Next, the
54 product testers and quality assurance engineers run tests to ensure the robustness of the system. Finally, the product is
55 released to users, generally by the team lead or product owner.
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57 Even this simplified overview of product development highlights the complexity of product development, as it
58 involves numerous factors such as time, capital, capabilities, skills, and organisational structure. With the increasing
59 business interest in ML-powered applications, many organisations are incorporating additional steps to integrate *smart*
60 features into their existing products. This integration introduces new challenges, concerning fairness, security, and
61 privacy regarding data and model governance. Addressing these concerns is crucial, as failing to do so can lead to
62 serious reputational harm and potential ethical violations [3].
63

64 Integrating fairness considerations into each of these stages is essential to developing ethical and unbiased ML-
65 powered applications. In product development, bias can occur in multiple stages, including data collection, where
66 the selection of data sources may inadvertently reflect existing prejudices; model training, where algorithms might
67 learn and propagate these biases; and evaluation, where inadequate metrics can fail to detect unfair outcomes [4].
68 Additionally, deployment and user interaction phases can introduce new biases or exacerbate existing ones if not
69 carefully monitored. Addressing bias at each of these stages requires a comprehensive approach that spans technical,
70 social, and legal perspectives, ensuring that fairness is embedded throughout the entire product lifecycle.
71

72 Existing solutions for bias detection and mitigation are generally specific to particular stages of development. For
73 instance, product owners can utilise tools like the Microsoft RAI Toolbox [6] during the requirements stage, while
74 developers might use IBM Fair360 [2] to evaluate their models. Meanwhile, legal and business teams focus on examining
75 relevant regulations and standards. However, effectively sharing best practices among teams and developing a common
76 language for fairness depends largely on the organisational skills and coordination efforts within the business.
77

78 To integrate fairness solutions in every stage effectively, it is essential to provide development teams with practical
79 tools and frameworks that can guide them in incorporating fairness into their ML applications. Development teams,
80 especially those in SMEs, often lack the specialized knowledge and resources required to navigate the complexities
81 of fairness in ML. Therefore, creating detailed, easy-to-follow, standardised recipes/blueprints/flows for product
82 development pipelines can significantly aid these teams. These resources should clarify the consequences of various
83 fairness-improving techniques, enabling better decision-making and communication among stakeholders. This paper,
84 following some established practices from product development processes, proposes a management flow strategy for
85 fair ML development.
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90 2 AN EXAMPLE FAIRNESS MANAGEMENT FLOW

91
92 The existing CI/CD workflows in the software engineering domain can inspire us to define a standardised management
93 flow for clearly addressing responsibilities among different teams. Software engineering product lifecycles are already
94 bound to structured processes such as Scrum, and existing CI/CD flows leverage these methodologies to be effectively
95 utilised. In a typical CI/CD flow, developers define automated processes, regular assessments, and collaborative efforts
96 to release robust products. This kind of approach can support the desired communication between data scientists,
97 developers, legal experts, and business leaders. In this flow, the responsibilities can be shared like:
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99

- 100 • **Data scientists** are responsible for implementing fairness metrics and bias detection algorithms. They regularly
101 evaluate models for disparate impact and adjust data or model parameters to minimise bias. They review the
102 most detailed report.
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104

- **Developers** incorporate fairness checks and balances into the CI/CD pipeline. They ensure that model updates undergo fairness evaluation before deployment.
- **Business analysts and product owners** establish organisational policies for fairness and bias mitigation and ensure all teams are aligned with these policies.
- **User researchers and designers** engage with diverse stakeholders to enable equitable outcomes for all and collect feedback to improve the next iteration of the development.

An example *technical* implementation can potentially be implemented with a combination of GitHub Workflows and Actions [5] as illustrated in Figure 2. The CI/CD pipeline can be configured using a YAML file to automate fairness checks and generate outputs for multiple teams. **Integrating this kind of CI/CD flow opens up several research questions:**

- (1) During the design requirements modeling phase, what are the most effective approaches to designing these blueprints to ensure comprehensive coverage of fairness principles?
- (2) In the development stage, how can developers and data scientists establish effective communication through a shared codebase to collaboratively address fairness issues?
- (3) For evaluation purposes, various fairness notions (e.g., demographic parity, equalized odds, equal opportunity) can be utilised. How can we enable effective interpretation of these diverse metrics from a cross-disciplinary perspective?
- (4) In the deployment stage, generating multiple reports simultaneously is possible. With various static and interactive visualization tools available (e.g., Google PAIR’s What-If Tool [8], Fairness Indicators [7]), which visualization methods can be most effectively utilised to meet the different needs of various teams?

We aim to discuss these questions with researchers from diverse backgrounds. This interdisciplinary dialogue will help us refine our approaches and incorporate diverse perspectives into our research.

3 DATA AND MODEL GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS

Team-level accountability: With the increasing model size and capabilities, governance (and accountability) of the models and training/inference data is a growing concern. In traditional systems, GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and equivalent regulations provide a legislative structure for data governance, ensuring that personal data is handled responsibly and transparently. It defines specific roles such as data controllers and data processors, with clear responsibilities for managing and protecting personal data. When translating these roles to ML-powered systems, there are gaps in addressing fairness. For example, there is no clear responsibility for ethical and fair sourcing and the oversight of possible bias. A *fairness management flow* can help structure accountability in this process.

Regulatory compliance: With the implementation of the EU AI Act, businesses operating in the EU are now required to meet data quality and bias mitigation standards. This legislation mandates that organisations ensure their

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stages:
  - data_preprocessing
  - model_training
  - bias_evaluation
  ...
  - deployment
jobs:
  data_preprocessing:
    stage: data_preprocessing
    script:
      - python preprocess_data.py
    artefacts:
      paths:
        - dev/
        - fair-eval/
  ...
  bias_evaluation:
    stage: bias_evaluation
    script:
      - python evaluate_bias.py
    artefacts:
      reports:
        - dev/bias_report.html
        - fair/bias_report.html
        - exec/bias_report.html
        - design/bias_report.html
  ...

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Fig. 2. A sample YAML configuration file in this proposed flow. Different scripts, tests and artefacts can be defined in one workflow to be distributed to different stakeholders.

AI systems are developed and maintained with high-quality, unbiased data. Failure to comply with these requirements can result in significant legal and financial repercussions, including hefty fines and potential legal actions. It is also aligned with the UK GDPR and Equality Act 2010.

Engaging open-source communities: Utilising these pre-defined flows can support interdisciplinary teams by providing a shared codebase with assigned responsibilities. This approach can also enable quick and effective engagement with open-source communities, by documenting the process regularly and transparently. The organisations can also benefit from the diverse perspectives within open-source communities.

Increasing productivity: The proposed flow aims to accelerate the integration of existing guidelines into technical development pipelines. Given the rapid advancements in the field, researchers, practitioners, big tech organisations, and governments are continually publishing new guidelines and best practices. (AI Standards Hub's Database [1] returned around 350 standards on May '24, and these search results do not include guidelines/format-requirements published by open-source initiatives i.e. Mozilla, MLCommons, or big tech organisations i.e. Google, Meta, Microsoft) For development teams with limited resources, keeping up with these developments can be challenging. The proposed *fairness management flow* can facilitate the adoption of these evolving standards, ensuring that teams can stay up-to-date and implement the latest fairness practices efficiently and effectively.

4 CONCLUSION

Sharing responsibilities among stakeholders is crucial for effective governance. This means defining clear roles and responsibilities for data scientists, developers, legal experts, and business leaders. The existing tools, practices and techniques from the system engineering domain can guide researchers and practitioners to develop effective collaborative governance frameworks that can help ensure that all aspects of data and model management are addressed with automated and transparent processes. As ML applications continue to evolve, robust data and model governance will be essential for maintaining fairness, security, and privacy. The proposed *fairness management flow* can support cross-disciplinary product development teams to ensure the robustness of bias detection and mitigation in their development pipelines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is a part of *Proactive Monitoring of AI Fairness*, which is supported by Innovate UK [Project No: 10108523].

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